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L.i.F.E - Lifestyle for Environment: A Path Towards Sustainable Development

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INTRODUCTION

By 2050, the world's population may reach a whopping 10 billion and with more people comes more demand for – food, fashion, travel, housing and related aspirations. An increasing number of people are unable to meet basic needs while two to three billion new urban consumers and youth will receive the majority of their information from social media. In a world stretched thin for resources and under the threat of global biodiversity loss and climate change, our lifestyles decisions are putting the planet at risk. We need targeted action. India as a country can find out the solutions of Sustainable Development by approaching our roots of Culture & Lifestyle & move forward on the path of Development. There can be many ways of decreasing our carbon footprints just by changing our present behavior of consumption & modern lifestyle by going back to our traditional living. We can better manage our Natural Resources by continuing the practices of environment conservation of ancient india. Development does not only mean modernization & hence westernization rather it is PEACE,

HARMONY & WELLBEING of all living creatures present on the Earth. Sustainable living means understanding how our lifestyle choices impact the world around us and finding ways for everyone to live better and lighter. [1]

Figure 1: LiFE – Lifestyle For Environment: Spearheading the quest for a sustainable planet
 Source: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pxmWoD_eLA

What is Lifestyle for Environment?

This movement calls for coming together with collective participation, to take lifestyle for environment forward as a campaign and as a mass movement for environmentally conscious

Figure 2: The ring of lifestyles: layers of influence on needs and wants
 Source: https://www.oneplanetnetwork.org/sites/default/files/a_framework_for_sustainable_lifestyles_determinants_and_strategies_0

life style in a manner that revolutionizes many sectors and diverse areas such as fishing, agriculture, wellness, dietary choices, packaging, housing, hospitality, tourism, clothing, fashion, water management and energy. The idea is based on mindful and deliberate utilization of resources, instead of mindless and destructive consumption.

The idea of 'LIFE' is to be taken ahead as a mass campaign to nudge the people to adopt environment conscious lifestyles. [2]

Components of LIFE

- **From dispose economy to circular economy:** In a linear/dispose economy we mine raw materials that we process into a product that is thrown away after use. In a circular economy, we close the cycles of all these raw materials. It aims to increase the lifecycle of goods through reuse, recycling and repairs.
- **3Ps – Pro Planet People:** People and planet are interconnected. Life as we know today cannot exist if either are destroyed. The aim is to encourage people to lead the lifestyle having a smaller carbon footprint, leading to a more sustainable use of the environment.
- **Eliminating/ Reducing throw away culture:** Under throwaway culture, economy is strongly influenced by consumerism. It features overconsumption and a preference for short-lived products, which maximize profit, rather than creating

durable goods that don't need constant replacing.

- **One World:** Climate change is a global phenomenon. No individual country has the ability to solve this problem alone. Thus, there is need for international cooperation and coordination to better tackle the challenge. [3]

Figure 3: Shifting from 'take, make, dispose' to a circular, regenerative model.
Source: <https://www.thinkwood.com/blog/coming-full-circle-designing-for-end-of-life>

Drivers of Lifestyle of a person/ Society

Income level: This is one of the strongest lifestyle indicators and drivers of consumption. Also, there is compounded social pressure to maintain lifestyle levels once adopted.

Values: Many consider values as the foundation of lifestyle decisions as people tend to consume to fulfil value-laden objectives. Values can be at the personal or broader cultural or ethical levels.

Ability: People's abilities are influenced by many things e.g. age, geography, climatic conditions, which in turn affect lifestyle

decisions.

Awareness: Awareness of consumption impacts, at the individual and collective levels, can shape choices. Awareness can have a multiplier effect.

Knowledge: The availability (or the lack) of knowledge and information on products, services, and alternative options can often encourage or hinder lifestyles choices.

Social norms and peers: Our lifestyles are heavily influenced by those around us: family background, social circles, colleague expectations, professional decorum and social practices.

Media: The media with its far reach into our lives is one of the strongest influences on values, social norms and lifestyles, spreading and accelerating the social norms of consumerism.

Market prices: Market prices determine who can afford market options. When more sustainable products or services are priced higher than the less sustainable alternatives, the sustainable option is less competitive

Technology: Characteristics such as complexity, resource efficiency, indigenouslyness, and affordability influence the uptake and use of technologies.

Policies and institutional frameworks: These 2 have a powerful influence on all stakeholders and lifestyle directions. Hard (e.g. penalties and subsidies) and soft (e.g. nudging and voluntary standards) policy instruments can shift the entire consumption architecture. [4]

Determinants of lifestyles

While motivations and driving factors explain the need or desire for a particular lifestyle or consumption practice, they translate into action only when certain determinants are in place. Determinants are meta-factors that establish whether or not a lifestyle is practiced or sustainable. Based on their characteristics, determinants can be grouped as: i) attitudes, ii) facilitators/access, and iii) infrastructure.

i. Attitudes: Attitudes are a cluster of factors that contribute to a person's value orientation and their likelihood to consume. They determine preferences and choices – e.g. people who are health-conscious and eat less meat or are vegetarian tend to express pro-environment or religious attitudes.

ii. Facilitators/Access: Belonging to a community network can facilitate access to certain local goods or services. In the same vein, a government policy can facilitate development of more competitive renewable energy options. Facilitators are a set of factors that contribute to the possibility for certain behavioral patterns or a lifestyle to actualize. Having a propensity to lead a consumerist lifestyle is not enough; one must have access to the consumer goods and services, social networks, etc., that make up that lifestyle. Access reflects 'agency,' or the ability to take personally meaningful actions.

iii. Infrastructure: This refers to socio-ecological interfaces that support consumption

activities. They include the physical infrastructure (for housing, mobility, and leisure) and the design of systems of provision (e.g. pricing and capacities of utilities like water and energy). Infrastructure around housing and transportation, for example, would need to be accessible, safe, dependable, etc., and because it lasts a long time and tends to lock users into particular behavior pattern patterns throughout their operational lifespan, need to be highly sustainable. [5]

SUSTAINABLE LIFESTYLE & INDIAN CULTURE

The Indian conception of life is embodied in a coherent world-view in which all its aspects exist in a state of inter-related harmony, being governed by a universal order that is reflected in all realms of human experience. The human

being is part of a well-ordered system in which all aspects of life and nature have their place, and are not in opposition, but in harmony with each other. This harmony between humans and nature is integral to the Indian tradition and ethos. [6]

TRADITIONAL INDIAN LIFESTYLE PRACTICES

Traditional Indian Lifestyle can give us hundreds of examples of living in harmony with nature. Living a life of moderation & giving back to nature is not new to us.

Annually, approximately 500 billion plastic bags are used worldwide.

More than one million bags are used every minute.

An average global person wastes 2.5 litres of water in a day, in brushing, bathing, utensils, laundry, etc.

Turning off lights, ACs and heaters when not in use can save up to 282 kilowatts of energy per day.

30 minutes of idling at traffic signals wastes nearly 1 litre of fuel.

Figure_5: Individual Action is the Core of Climate Responsibility

Source: niti.gov.in/sites/default/files/2022-04/Brochure_LIFE_vf_with_Cropmarks_19042022

A. NATURE CONSERVATION

In India, forests are revered and trees worshipped. Forest and tree cover in India stand at 24.01 per cent of the country's geographical area and is on ascendance. Forests neutralize approximately 12 per cent of India's GHG emissions. [6]

Sacred Groves: Conservation of sacred species, groves, forests and landscapes has been an important aspect of the ethics of Indian culture. The Sacred Groves / Forests are important repositories of floral and faunal diversity that have been conserved by local communities in a sustainable manner.

Bishnoi Community: Bishnoi is a social group found in the Western Thar Desert of India, who follows the tenets of conserving biodiversity of the area and ensuring a healthy eco-friendly social life for the community. For them, harming the environment means harming themselves.

Khejri Tree Conservation: In Rajasthan, a desert state of India, the Khejri tree (*Prosopis cineraria*) is valued for its moisture-retaining properties, and it is not axed even if it comes between the constructions.

Traditional Rain water harvesting systems of India: Indians Communities are harvesting rain water since centuries as we knew the importance & scarcity of fresh water since long time. These rain water harvesting systems are specific & Unique according to the topography, climate & Rain at that location.

Step Wells of Gujarat, Tanks of Tamil Nadu, johads of Rajasthan & Zabo System of Nagaland are few examples.

B. FOOD

Food production, processing, marketing, consumption and disposal have important environmental externalities because of energy and natural resource usage and associated GHG emissions. [6]

Locally Grown & Seasonal foods: Eating locally grown & season produces are recommended for good health, which significantly reduces the need for preservation & transportation of food. Eating seasonal is primarily encouraged by our traditional system of medicine.

Energy Saving Techniques of Cooking: Various energy saving techniques like hand, grinding & hand churning using madani. Food preservation has also been done in a very environment friendly manner without using energy generated by fossil fuels instead simple method of pickling, sun drying etc. General aversion to food wastage and respect for food are deeply ingrained in Indian psyche. Children in Indian homes are taught about respect for food at a young age. [7]

C. SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION VALUES

Simple sustainable consumption values, such as switching off unwanted Electrical appliances are imbibed in homes. people often prefer to sleep out in the open, in courtyards or

on the terrace, thus leading to reduced usage of cooling appliances in homes. The practice of sun-drying of clothes and hand washing dishes reduces the usage of energy-intensive tumble driers and dish-washers, respectively. Hand washing the dishes would save around 200 to 300kWh/year assuming one cycle per day of dish washing. [6]

D. CLOTHING

India is a home to many unique types of hand woven fabrics or handlooms. Traditional practice of weaving textile with a weaving

India will get its non-fossil energy capacity to 500 gigawatt by 2030

India will meet 50 per cent of its energy requirements till 2030 with renewable energy

India will reduce its projected carbon emission by one billion tonnes by 2030

India will reduce the carbon intensity of its economy by 45 per cent by 2030

India will achieve net zero by 2070

India's Panchamrit: A Fivefold Strategy to combat climate change
-Prime Minister Narendra Modi at COP 26

loom does not require any energy, it only requires the skill to weave. Also we have a rich heritage of various hand embroidered fabrics. Examples like banarsi kanjivaram, patola , zardozi, kalamkari, tye & dye, sujani, phulkari, kashida, kantha, Nagaland weaves etc.[8]

Khadi: Khadi is made from cotton, silk or wool. Yarn spinning by charkha & woven manually, i.e. without any electric support (not utilizing any fossil fuel), if dyed with natural dye, it becomes green fabric. Production of one meter of khadi fabric consumes just three liters of water against 55 liters consumed in a traditional textile mill. This hand woven fabric has the smallest carbon footprint. [9]

CONCLUSION:

One crucial step to support lifestyle for environment (LIFE) requires understanding the patterns of different types of lifestyles – known as lifestyle segmentation. Each lifestyle segment has and manifests distinct values, preferences, and practices in areas such as fashion, use of language, and leisure activities. There is a need for countries, regions and cities to conduct social-ecological segmentation to design targeted interventions solutions and better responses.

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